

Investigation of algorithm mentions in abstracts of LIS papers

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Introduction

As scientific research moves into the fourth paradigm of "data-intensive research," algorithms have become increasingly crucial in scientific research. Especially in the interdisciplinary domain, e.g. Library and Information Science (LIS). Therefore, it is necessary to identify the algorithms used in the LIS domain and reveal the high-frequency algorithms and the chronological distribution of abstracts containing algorithms, which can help researchers better understand the development of algorithms in this domain. Compared with full-text academic papers, the abstracts of academic papers are the authors' highly condensed academic results, and the algorithms appearing in the abstracts of academic papers are more likely to be the algorithms actually used by the authors, which are more representative of the domain applications. Therefore, this paper will study the abstract data based on the core journal papers in the domain of LIS. Specifically, this paper explores the following three questions.

RQ1. How to automatically identify the algorithms mentioned in the abstracts of LIS papers?

RQ2. What are the algorithms mentioned in the abstracts of LIS papers with high frequency?

RQ3. What are the chronological distribution characteristics of the abstracts of academic papers that mention algorithms in the LIS domain?

RQ1 forms the foundation for answering research RQ2 and RQ3. The answers to RQ2 and RQ3 reveal the application and development of algorithms in the LIS domain from two different perspectives.

Related Work

With the advancements in deep-learning technology, researchers have begun to apply these techniques to extract knowledge entities such as algorithms, datasets, and software tools from academic texts. This allows for the conduct of more accurate entity measurement analyses. For example, Wang et al. (2021) used the BiLSTM+CRFs model to automatically extract algorithmic entities from academic texts in the Chinese IS domain. The study found that the three most frequently used algorithms in academic papers in the Chinese IS domain are "TF-IDF", "Vector space model", and "SVM" algorithms.

Methodology

Guided by the idea of remote supervision, this study collects and builds an algorithmic dictionary from various data sources. A "silver standard" corpus is constructed through rule-based matching, containing algorithmic annotations. The annotated corpus is subsequently used to train deep learning models. The extracted algorithms are then subject to exploratory analysis. It is important to note that the focus of this study is the annotation and extraction of nouns or noun phrases representing algorithms and models within the abstracts.

Data collection

We collect abstracts of LIS papers based on the list of core journals of the domain of LIS in *JCR 2021 (Journal Citation Reports 2021)*; Journal Citation Report is published annually by *Clarivate Analytics* that includes core journals in different domains with certain domain authority. A total of 84 journals in the domain of LIS, including JASIST and IPM, are included in the JCR 2021, and their bibliographic data is collected from 1990 to 2021. In this paper, only the abstract data of research articles are included in the study. After data cleaning, we obtain a total of 67,141 abstracts which constitutes the dataset of the study.

Algorithm annotated silver corpus creation

We first collect algorithm terms from Google Scholar, Wikipedia, and related machine learning and deep learning literature to construct an algorithm dictionary containing 390 distinct algorithms. The algorithm dictionary is then used to match across the study dataset, resulting in 2,256 abstracts containing a total of 2,953 algorithms. The pre-labeled data is then subjected to manual review and labeling to ensure accuracy. Through this process, a final dataset of 2,111 abstracts containing 3,801 algorithms (with a total of 507 unique algorithms) is obtained to serve as the annotated corpus.

Automatic algorithm extraction

We build a pre-trained language model + deep neural network architecture for algorithms extraction. Among them, BERT (<https://github.com/google-research/bert>) or SciBERT (<https://github.com/allenai/scibert>) is used for text characterization, BiLSTM network is applied to

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obtain contextual dependencies and extract key feature information, and CRFs model is used for annotation of label sequences. To train and evaluate the automatic algorithm extraction model, we divide the annotated data into a training set, a validation set, and a test set with a ratio of 8:1:1.

Result

Extraction result of the algorithm

In this study, we train four automatic algorithm extraction models and evaluate the model performance using P, R, and F₁ values. According to the results of the four models in Table 1, the SciBERT+BiLSTM+CRFs perform the best, with the highest F₁ value at 74.55%.

Table 1. Evaluation of models

Model	P(%)	R(%)	F ₁ (%)
BERT+CRFs	67.61	69.03	68.31
SciBERT+CRFs	71.79	74.80	73.26
BERT+BiLSTM+CRFs	70.64	67.45	69.00
SciBERT+BiLSTM+CRFs	73.78	75.33	74.55

Frequency of the algorithm mentions

We count the mentioned frequency of different algorithms in the abstracts of LIS papers. The algorithm mentioned frequency refers to the number of times an algorithm is mentioned in an abstract. Note that if an algorithm is mentioned multiple times in a single abstract, it is counted only once in this study. Table 2 shows the top 10 most frequently mentioned algorithms.

Table 2. Top 10 algorithms mentioned in abstracts of LIS papers

No.	Algorithm	Freq.
1	Structural Equation Modeling(SEM)	1,123
2	Logistic Regression(LR)	454
3	Support Vector Machine(SVM)	228
4	Neural Networks(NN)	200
5	Linear Regression(LR)	183
6	Multiple Regression(MR)	158
7	Decision Tree(DT)	139
8	Random Forest(RF)	129
9	Convolutional Neural Network(CNN)	120
10	Latent Dirichlet Allocation(LDA)	108

As shown in Table 2, among the top three most frequently mentioned algorithms, "Structural Equation Modeling" is a widely used algorithm for multivariate data analysis, "Logistic Regression" is a well-established algorithm for binary classification problems, and "Support Vector Machine" is considered one of the top 10 algorithms for data mining (Wu et al., 2008). We find that the top 10 algorithms mentioned include a mix of traditional statistical machine learning algorithms (such as "DT") as well as newer deep-learning algorithms (such as "CNN"). This reflects that scholars in the

domain of LIS are keeping up with the times in the selection and use of algorithms.

Time evolution of the algorithm mentions

We perform algorithm extraction on the total volume of data using the trained optimal algorithm extraction model, of which algorithms are extracted from 6814 abstracts, representing roughly 10.1% of the total data. This reflects that there is still a fraction of scholars in the LIS domain who are willing to mention the algorithms they use in abstracts with space limitations. Figure 1 illustrates the distribution of abstracts that mention algorithms by year. Considering the difference in the number of publications in different years, we use the ratio of the number of abstracts mentioning algorithms to the total number of abstracts in that year for the statistics. The results indicate that while the overall proportion of abstracts mentioning algorithms in academic papers in the LIS domain is not high, it shows a steady upward trend, highlighting the growing importance of algorithms in this field.

Figure 1. Ratio of abstracts mentioning algorithms per year

Conclusion

This study presents an automatic algorithm extraction model and investigates the frequently mentioned algorithms in abstracts of academic papers from the LIS domain and the trend of algorithmic mentions over time. Our findings indicate that the most frequently mentioned algorithm in the abstracts of academic papers is "SEM". Additionally, over time, researchers in the LIS domain seem to be mentioning algorithms more frequently in their abstracts, indicating the increasing significance of algorithms in this field.

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References

- Wang, Y., Zhang, H. & Zhang, C. (2021). Algorithm Entities Usage in Chinese Academic Articles from the Domain of Information Science. In *Proceedings of 18th International Conference on Scientometrics and Informetrics (ISSI2021)* (pp. 1559-1560). Leuven, Belgium.
- Wu, X., Kumar, V., Ross Quinlan, J., Ghosh, J., Yang, Q., Motoda, H., et al. (2008). Top 10 algorithms in data mining. *Knowledge and Information Systems*, 14(1), 1-37.